

Modeling of Damage and Residual Load-Bearing Capacity of Non-Crimp Fabric Composites

M. Kazemian, Ph.D. Candidate
 A. Cherniaev, Ph.D. P.Eng., Assoc. Prof.
 Department of Mechanical, Automotive and Materials Engineering, University of Windsor, Ontario, Canada

Background

Material: Unidirectional Non-Crimp Carbon Fabrics (NCF).

Advantage: combination of high mechanical properties and excellent manufacturability.

Applications: load-bearing aerospace structures, automotive parts, and wind energy components.

Structure: multiple straight and parallel yarn bands joined by polyester stitching (binder).

Problem: in-service damage can be a cause for severe reduction in load-carrying capacity of NCF composites.

Numerical modeling can provide cost-efficient solution for accessing damage and post-impact (residual) load-carrying capacity of NCF parts, as well as accelerated decision making.

Goal of this study: Evaluate the applicability of the commonly used composite material model available in LS-DYNA (MAT54) for predicting damage and residual load bearing capacity in structural elements made of NCF.

- MAT54:**
- strength criterion-based model.
 - multiple non-physical parameters governing post-failure behavior of the material.

Methodology

Manufacturing

Material: 12K UD intermediate modulus non-crimp carbon fabric pre-impregnated with epoxy resin. Areal density – 140 g/m², resin content – 38±3%.

Manufacturing: PLC oven at 132 °C (4 °C/min ramp rate, holding for 4 hours). Pressure: mold closing screws.

Experimental work

Material characterization

Property	Units	Value	Method
Longitudinal Young's modulus, E ₁	MPa	149018	
Transverse Young's modulus, E ₂	MPa	6071	ASTM D 3039
Major in-plane Poisson's ratio, ν ₁₂	-	0.32	
In-plane shear modulus, G ₁₂	MPa	4217	10° off-axis
Longitudinal tensile strength, X _t	MPa	2060	ASTM D 3039
Longitudinal compressive strength*, X _c	MPa	814	Modified ASTM D695
Transverse tensile strength, Y _t	MPa	29.1	ASTM D 3039
alcTransverse compressive strength*, Y _c	MPa	121	Modified ASTM D695
In-plane shear strength, S _c	MPa	44.5	10° off-axis
Longitudinal tensile strain-at-failure, ε _{1f}	%	1.37	ASTM D 3039
Transverse tensile strain-at-failure, ε _{2f}	%	0.40	ASTM D 3039
In-plane shear strain-at-failure, γ _{12f}	%	1.71	10° off-axis
Longitudinal compressive strain-at-failure, ε _{1f}	%	0.55	Modified ASTM D695
Transverse compressive strain-at-failure, ε _{2f}	%	1.99	Modified ASTM D695
Mode I strain energy release rate, G _{IC}	kJ/m ²	0.66	ASTM 5528b
Mode II strain energy release rate, G _{IIc}	kJ/m ²	2.77	ENF bending

Component testing

Numerical model

LS-DYNA MODEL FOR PHASE I & PHASE II LOADING

DELAMINATION MODEL (OPTION 9 TIEBREAK)

Property	Unit	Value
NFLS	MPa	75.00
SFLS	MPa	43.30
G _{1c}	kJ/m ²	0.66
G _{2c}	kJ/m ²	2.77
CN	MPa/mm	200.000
CT2CN	-	0.37

NON-PHYSICAL PARAMETERS OF MAT54

Parameter	Description
SLIMT1	Factor to determine the minimum stress limit after stress maximum (fiber tension).
SLIMC1	Factor to determine the minimum stress limit after stress maximum (fiber tension).
SLIMT2	Factor to determine the minimum stress limit after stress maximum (matrix tension).
SLIMC2	Factor to determine the minimum stress limit after stress maximum (matrix compression).
SLIMS	Factor to determine the minimum stress limit after stress maximum (shear).
YCFAC	Reduction factor for compressive fiber strength X _c after matrix compressive failure

Results

Multiple non-physical parameters combinations were studied

- Phase I: only few outliers
- Phase II: only few accurate predictions (e.g., case 21 below)

Sensitivity study evaluated the effect of individual non-physical parameters of MAT54 on Phase II modeling results:

Conclusions

- Reasonably accurate predictions of load-bearing capacity of damaged NCF parts can be achieved using MAT54 but require identification of its non-physical parameters.
- For compression-dominated loading, SLIMC1 appears to be the most influencing non-physical parameter.